

Community Perception on Management of Green Open Space (RTH) in Pontianak City

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Abstract: This research is based on the "Indonesia Green Award" obtained by the City of Pontianak in the category of Green City, the results of this award are one of the efforts of the Pontianak City government in building and managing green space. The purpose of this study was to find out how people's perceptions of the management of Green Open Space in Pontianak City. The research method used in this study is a descriptive survey method with interview techniques and questionnaire aids. The approach used is a quantitative approach. The result is that the perception of the majority of respondents regarding the management of Green Open Space in general is good, but it cannot be denied that there are still a small number of respondents who disagree with the management of Green Open Space that has been able to meet the RTH standards.

Keywords: Green Open Space, Pontianak City, Green Open Space, City Park, Equator

I. Introduction

This study focuses on community perceptions on the management of Green Open Space (RTH) in Pontianak City. This research is based first, on the "Indonesia Green Award" award obtained by the Pontianak City Green City category, the results of this award are one of the efforts of the Pontianak City government in building and managing green space (Fai, 2017). Secondly, based on research by Rinai Domenri Erwin and colleagues researching the determination of the priority of green open space in Pontianak using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method with the results of the analysis showing the need for green open space in Pontianak based on the area is 32.35 km², and the needs of green space based on the number of the population until 2027 is 15.67 km² (Erwin, 2016). Third, based on research conducted by Dwi Marisa Midyanti and colleagues who researched recommendations on the form of green open space in Pontianak using AHP-COPRAS method, with the results obtained the best alternative to form green open space in Pontianak City which has the results of AHP-COPRAS calculation, namely the area rainwater absorption (Midyanti, 2018). Fourth, based on the results of research conducted by Nada Alifia on the identification of the location and type of green space in urban settlements, with the results of the location of the research object that is Pontianak City, Paal Lima Village does not or does not yet have green open space that is able to support all the needs and comfort of the community (Alifa, 2016).

Green Open Space (RTH) in urban areas, which are regulated according to Law No. 26 of 2007 concerning Spatial Planning, the minimum area to guarantee the existence and sustainability of urban green space, is 30% of the total area of the city. Based on the Guidelines of the Directorate General of Spatial Planning of the Department of Public Works in 2017, there are at least three functions of green space, namely Bio Ecological (related to the environment), Social Economy (Productive), Urban Ecosystems, and Aesthetics (Beauty). However, a report from the Department of Public Works and Spatial Planning, it is known that currently in Pontianak City has a green space area of only 21.38 km² or 19.8% of the area of Pontianak City. Of course this figure has not been able to reach the minimum standard of 30% that has been determined by the central government regulated by the Act. In line with the efforts of the local government to increase or increase the development of Green City in Pontianak to 30%, this research needs to be done to assess the level of comfort for urban communities towards existing green space. So that the hope of adding green open space Pontianak City together with increased public satisfaction with green open space itself.

Demands on increasing the comfort of green space for urban communities are increasingly prominent, thus encouraging the need to conduct a study of green space management in order to be able to provide satisfaction to urban communities and to form cities with dynamic environments. This study wants to try to explore how people's

perceptions of the management of Green Open Space in Pontianak City. Researcher Contribution; first, theoretically this research can provide benefits for the development of discourse in the field of management and development of Green Open Space. Second, Provide information about public perceptions of the management of Green Open Spaces in Pontianak City. Indirectly provide a view of the government both in the city of Pontianak and in other areas, in managing and developing Green Open Space.

II. Empirical Study

Public perception can be a potential success in the development and management of Green Open Space in Pontianak City. Community participation in the management and development of Green Open Space is very important, this effort is to prevent the occurrence of irregularities in the use of Green Open Space (Januarisa, 2015). Management management in the maintenance of good Green Open Space is involving the community to become the manager of Green Open Space, by making a shared responsibility for creating a dynamic Green Open Space (Husna, 2017).

The influence of the quality of the Green Open Space on the motivation to visit the community greatly influences, the quality of the Green Open environment which consists of elements of cleanliness, security, visitor circulation, park vitality, park supporting facilities, image (impression) of a park, as well as the aesthetics of the park have a positive influence on motivation and desire to visit respondents. From these seven variables, each has a different effect on the respondent. This can be seen from the condition of the existing parks and management efforts in each park (Fatwadi, 2011).

One of the Green Open Spaces owned by Pontianak City, Waterfront City, has a positive impact on the development of Pontianak City tourism, especially in locations on the Kapuas river bank. Its location is close to the harbor of Pontianak City, so it plays a big role on the mobility and attractiveness of tourism in Pontianak City. The influence of existing potential makes a natural attraction that not all attractions in the city or region. The efforts according to Pontianak City government plans in the 2013-2033 RTRW and RPJMN 2015-2019 that the management of the Spatial Park of Kapuas Park reflect 4 design strategies namely continuity, variety, connections and sequences, so as to create tourist destinations that facilitate recreational activities based on waterfront city (Andrasromo, 2018).

Public perception of the management of urban parks (RTH) in the city of Bandung is quite good, but not a few also have the opposite perception. They stated that the management of city parks was not well maintained, lack of cleanliness and inadequate completeness of the park, and the maintenance of the park was still carried out incidentally by the management agency. Then discovered the fact that there is no institutional system that can accommodate all stakeholders in the management of city parks (Setiawan, 2017).

Positive results are shown in the perception of the people of the city of Palu on the existence of Green Open Space park GOR. The surrounding community uses the Green Open Space of the GOR park as a place to make a living, which can bring income to the community. And the green open space of the GOR park becomes one of the general targets for the community to interact socially between individuals (Lestari, 2016).

Green Open Space Indicates Integrity Teaching located at Jalan Ahmad Yani General Pekanbaru City with a fairly large area, utilized well by the city community to carry out recreational activities, sports activities, economic activities, interacting activities, and as a waiting room for bus stops. City communities as users are of the opinion that the existence of Green Open Space Indicates Integrity Teaching (Pratama, 2018).

The quality of urban parks (RTH) as a public space in the city of Surakarta shows that the elements of a city park with good conditions include the level of activity, while the elements of user service, meaningfulness and ease of access are at moderate conditions. The quality of city parks in Surakarta, namely the Park Complex of Manahan Stadium and Taman Balekambang, are in moderate condition. Based on the theory, issues, and analysis results related to city parks, the results are obtained that the quality of urban parks in the city of Surakarta is in good condition (Pramoto, 2019).

Conceptual Framework

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework

III. Research Methods

The research method used in this study is a descriptive survey method with interview techniques and questionnaire aids. The approach used is a quantitative approach. This research was conducted at the Green Open Space owned by Pontianak City in West Kalimantan province. The data used in this study were sourced from primary data and secondary data. Primary data were collected using questionnaire, interview and observation techniques. The population is visitors and have been to the location of the Green Open Space owned by the Pontianak City government. As for the sample in this study, there were 150 visitors of green open space in Pontianak City.

Data analysis was performed using qualitative analysis with a Likert scale model approach. According to Sugiyono (Sugiono, 2016), Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena.

IV. Discussion

To find out community perceptions on the management of Green Open Space (RTH) in Pontianak City will be analyzed based on the effective green space dimensions. There are four elements that become dimensions of effective green space and provide benefits to explain the discussion under study (Carmona, 2008), namely:

- 1) Comfort, is an element of user security from intrusion.
- 2) Relaxation, is comfort with man-made elements.
- 3) Passive and Active engagement, are elements of activities that are active or passive.
- 4) Discovery, is an element of activity that is attractive.

In the following, the researcher will describe the results of the research in the field based on the four dimensions of green space that have been described above and each of these dimensions is described as indicators as follows:

- 1) **Green Open Space Provides Means And Infrastructure In Supporting The Safety Of Visitors**

Table 1. Community Perceptions of Facilities and Infrastructure in Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Strongly agree	-	-	1	3,33	2	6,67	-	-	5	16,67	8	5,33
Agree	11	36,66	17	56,67	15	50,00	13	43,34	13	43,33	70	46,67
Neutral	11	36,67	1	3,33	4	13,33	10	33,33	9	30,00	35	23,33
Disagree Strongly	8	26,67	11	36,67	8	26,67	7	23,33	3	10,00	36	24,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	1	3,33	-	-	-	-	1	0,67
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Based on interviews with visitors they were of the opinion that the facilities and infrastructure to support security had good security, the banks of the river had been given a barrier, and there were employees to guard historical objects in the Equator Monument. As for those who disagree, say that security is still relatively standard, there is no special security in uniform, except if the location has a large event, and there is no security post. The Waterfront respondents who disagreed, argued that the length of the location of the area was not comparable to the existing security posts, moreover the security posts were not regularly maintained (sometimes empty). As a result, the location of the area is occupied by illegal traders who create green space locations.

RTH Korem has been managed well, visible security patrol on duty, the presence of CCTV, the visiting hours limit, guardrail, and park lighting. As for disagreeing, respondents consider that there are still many thugs who roam in the open space. Respondents of RTH Akcaya Garden rate, RTH does not have a security post, does not have a security / security, and does not have CCTV, so visitors do not feel safe. RTH Untan Garden, respondents considered that they do not have a large parking space, so parking capacity is limited to far from existing security monitoring.

- 2) **Availability of Security Guarantees in the event of Damage and Loss in the Garden Area**

Table 2. Public Perceptions About the Availability of Security Guarantees in Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	1	3,33	2	6,67	-	-	6	20,00	9	6,00
Agree	10	33,33	12	40,00	14	46,66	10	33,33	11	36,66	57	38,00
Neutral	12	40,00	7	23,34	5	16,67	7	23,34	5	16,67	36	24,00
Disagree Strongly	8	26,67	10	33,33	8	26,67	9	30,00	8	26,67	43	28,67
Disagree	-	-	-	-	1	3,33	4	13,33	-	-	5	3,33
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

All green open space respondents assume that with the existing security guard (parking) the security has a responsibility to maintain parking security. As for disagreeing, they have the experience of losing helmets / goods, but no substitute is obtained, the location is not protected by official security.

3) Visitors Feel Safe With Caring Available

Table 3. Community Perceptions About Safety When Visiting Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	1	3,33	2	6,67	1	3,33	7	23,34	11	7,33
Agree	9	30,00	13	43,34	13	43,33	9	30,00	14	46,66	58	38,67
Neutral	14	46,66	9	30,00	6	20,00	9	30,00	9	30,00	47	31,34
Disagree Strongly	7	23,34	7	23,34	8	26,67	10	33,34	-	-	32	21,33
Disagree	-	-	-	-	1	3,33	1	3,33	-	-	2	1,33
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

The data above shows that respondents as visitors already feel safe with the existing safeguards, with the existence of guard posts. Other respondents argued that although there were guard posts, there were no guards in place and no patrol at the green space.

4) Tree Vegetation Provides Beautiful Open Green Space

Table 4. Community Perceptions About Vegetation Trees Provide Beautiful Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	4	13,33	3	10,00	2	6,67	9	30,00	18	12,00
Agree	17	56,67	12	40,00	27	90,00	24	80,00	18	60,00	98	65,33
Neutral	11	36,66	9	30,00	-	-	4	13,33	3	10,00	27	18,00
Disagree Strongly	2	6,67	5	16,67	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	4,67
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Based on interviews conducted with visitors to the trees in the location to make the atmosphere of green space to be shady and cool, and the trees that are relatively shady, lush, fresher and more varied so that adds to the beauty of green space. While the reason for the Equator Monument respondent disagrees because of the lack of equal distribution and unorganized trees in the location. Another reason for Waterfront respondents, the trees planted are not fertile and dry, seemingly neglected, coupled with the garbage of irresponsible visitors.

5) Green Open Facilities Support Convenience For Visitors

Table 5. Community Perceptions About Green Open Facilities Support Convenience for Visitors

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	3	10,00	3	10,00	-	-	11	36,66	17	11,33
Agree	20	66,66	17	56,66	27	90,00	25	83,33	12	40,00	100	66,67
Neutral	7	23,34	5	16,67	-	-	5	16,67	7	23,34	24	16,00
Disagree Strongly	3	10,00	5	16,67	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	6,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Based on interviews with RTH Tugu Khatulistiwa respondents assess the existing facilities are less able to meet the needs of visitors, lack of public toilets, not many places to sit, many park facilities are damaged / not maintained, not many places to shelter, and parking vehicles are not neat. Waterfont respondents stated that there are no public toilets available at the location, seating is only at part of the park location, and the garbage is full of rubbish in the trash, causing a bad odor. Other RTHs based on interviews with all three respondents have complete facilities, ranging from parking, toilets, seating, reading parks, children's playgrounds and can be used as a sports venue.

6) The creativity of Green Open Space Design Showcases and Conceptual Buildings

Table 6. Public Perceptions About the Design of Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	2	6,66	3	10,00	-	-	10	33,34	15	10,00
Agree	20	66,66	18	60,00	27	90,00	20	66,66	17	56,66	102	68,00
Neutral	8	26,67	5	16,67	-	-	8	26,67	3	10,00	24	16,00
Disagree Strongly	2	6,67	5	16,67	-	-	2	26,67	-	-	9	6,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

The Equator Monument and Akcaya Garden show that green space is still in its original form, although there are additions, but it does not change the original atmosphere much, giving the impression of nostalgia for the people who enjoy it. As for those who say disagree, they argue that the need for revamping the design to be more beautiful and modern. The other three green spaces expressed the same opinion that the design was conceptual. However, those who said they did not agree with the conceptual Waterfront, the reason was that the RTH location was considered too small and only extended so that visitors could not move freely in carrying out activities.

7) Easy Access to Green Open Space Locations

Table 7. Community Perception on the Ease of Access to Green Open Spaces

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	2	6,66	2	6,66	3	10,00	5	16,67	7	23,34	19	12,67
Agree	19	63,33	18	60,00	27	90,00	21	70,00	23	76,66	108	72,00
Neutral	7	23,34	5	16,67	-	-	4	13,33	-	-	16	10,66
Disagree Strongly	2	6,67	5	16,67	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	4,67

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Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Equator Monument is ideal and easily accessible, they think the location is on the edge of the highway and passed by public transportation. The opinion does not agree, because the location is far from the center of Pontianak and there is no expansion of the road to the location so that there is often a traffic jam when heading to the location. RTH Waterfront has easy access to the Waterfront location. They argue, the location is in the middle of the city so that it can be enjoyed by the community and the location is traversed by public transportation routes. But there are states not agree, because even though bypassed public transportation visitors still have to walk. While the other three green openings produced a positive response, namely the location is very easy to access because the three locations are in the middle of the city, alongside a highway, and traversed by public and online transportation.

8) Condition and Availability of Lighting Facilities as well as Plants in the Area of Green Open Space to Support the Creation of Beautiful Green Space

9)

Table 8. Community Perceptions About the Conditions and Availability of Lighting Facilities and Plants in the Green Open Area Support the Creation of Beautiful Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Strongly agree	1	3,33	3	10,00	3	10,00	1	3,33	9	30,00	17	11,33
Agree	12	40,00	18	60,00	27	90,00	22	73,33	17	56,67	96	64,00
Neutral	12	40,00	8	26,67	-	-	5	16,67	3	10,00	28	18,67
Disagree Strongly	5	16,67	1	3,33	-	-	2	6,67	1	3,33	9	6,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

The Equator Monument shows that there were respondents who disagreed because, not neatly arranged lights in lighting facilities, plus lights that were not bright and dead. Respondents of RTH Akcaya Garden and Untan Garden argued that they did not agree, they stated that there were still locations that were not yet well-lit, far from security scrutiny so that they were feared to lead to crime.

10) Green Open Space Provides Adequate Cleaning Facilities (Clean Water And Trash)

Table 9. Community Perception of Green Open Space Provides Cleaning Facilities

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Strongly agree	1	3,33	1	3,33	2	6,67	-	-	8	26,67	12	8,00
Agree	5	16,67	10	33,34	13	43,33	14	46,67	13	43,33	55	36,67
Neutral	13	43,33	11	36,67	6	20,00	9	30,00	8	26,67	47	31,33
Disagree Strongly	11	36,67	8	26,66	9	30,00	7	23,33	1	3,33	36	24,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

The Equator Monument respondents stated that the provision of clean water was very difficult to obtain. And respondents' criticism of available trash bins is not only as a complement, so it is not controlled by the RTH janitor. Waterfront respondents indicated that they thought that the RTH manager had tried to provide facilities but that all visitors must have a concern to be cared for together. With the availability of sanitation facilities in the form of clean water and adequate rubbish bins, based on interviews they regretted the rubbish bins were not in accordance with the volume of rubbish or the absence of sanitation workers in the field, so that the rubbish bin was filled to the point of falling and caused unpleasant odors.

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Other RTH respondents indicated that respondents assessed the existence of a toilet area with a guardian so that clean water could be controlled. But there are still those who disagree, their reason is that there are still many visitors littering, this is an indication of whether the visitor's character or visitors may be difficult to find an available trash.

11) Level of Ability of Green Open Space to Accommodate Activities of Visitors classified as Adequate

Table 10. Public Perceptions About the Ability of the Capacity of Green Open Space to Accommodate Visitor Activities classified as Adequate

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total		F	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	1	3,33	2	6,67	-	-	8	26,67	11	7,33		
Agree	11	36,66	11	36,67	27	90,00	15	50,00	15	50,00	79	52,67		
Neutral	10	33,34	12	40,00	1	3,33	11	36,67	7	23,33	41	27,33		
Disagree Strongly	9	30,00	6	20,00	-	-	4	13,33	-	-	19	12,67		
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100		

Source: processed data, 2019

The Equator Monument respondent shows that the limited space for visitors (RTH location is not extensive) makes visitors limited activity. The reason for their Waterfront respondents is that there are still many illegal traders entering restricted areas and using green space, which disrupts visitors' activities. As for Park Akcaya respondents, they disagreed, the reason was that there were not many seats that could accommodate many visitors, and the location did not have a view that could be enjoyed.

12) Diversity of Types of Play Facilities / Activities Sufficient for Visitors

Table 11. Community Perception About Diversity Types of Play Facilities / Activities Sufficient for Visitors

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total		F	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	-	-	2	6,67	1	3,33	11	36,66	14	9,33		
Agree	10	33,33	18	60,00	28	93,33	15	50,00	12	40,00	83	55,33		
Neutral	10	33,33	5	16,67	-	-	8	26,67	5	16,67	28	18,67		
Disagree Strongly	10	33,34	7	23,33	-	-	6	20,00	2	6,67	25	16,67		
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100		

Source: processed data, 2019

The Equator Monument shows that there are a lot of empty spaces that are not used so that the manager does not seem to maximize the existing location, can be used as a reading room or other. Waterfront respondents felt they felt the location provided was inadequate for concert, exhibition and bazaar activities. As for the next two green open spaces, Akcaya Garden and Untan Garden, respondents said that the location was very flexible, starting from morning for sports to night for the night market, coupled with reading park facilities.

13) Condition of Facilities and Infrastructure (Seats, Gazebos, Shelters, Play Facilities, Other Assistance and Support)

Available and Can Be Used Well

Table 12. Community Perception of the Condition of Facilities and Infrastructure

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	1	3,33	1	3,33	2	6,67	1	3,33	7	23,33	12	8,00
Agree	7	23,33	18	60,00	28	93,33	16	53,33	17	56,67	86	57,33
Neutral	8	26,67	4	13,34	-	-	10	33,34	6	20,00	28	18,67
Disagree Strongly	14	46,67	7	23,33	-	-	3	10,00	-	-	24	16,00
Disagree	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Tugu Khatulistiwa respondents stated that there was a construction of new facilities and infrastructure, but it was not properly guarded / cared for, either by irresponsible visitors or the management's inability to guard against irresponsible visitors. RTH Waterfront respondents considered that there is still a lack of seats, play facilities, toilets, which can accommodate a large volume of visitors. RTH Akcaya Garden shows that respondents assess existing facilities and infrastructure, but are not sufficient to meet the volume of visitors.

14) Availability of Ease of Access to the Use of Facilities Available in Green Open Space

Table 13. Public Perception of the Ease of Access to the Use of Facilities Available in Green Open Space

Selection	The Equator Monument		Waterfront		Korem		Akcaya Garden		Untan Garden		Total	F
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Strongly agree	-	-	5	16,67	2	6,67	1	3,33	6	20,00	14	9,33
Agree	11	36,67	17	56,66	28	93,33	16	53,33	18	60,00	90	60,00
Neutral	-	-	5	16,67	-	-	12	40,00	6	20,00	23	15,33
Disagree Strongly	8	26,67	3	10,00	-	-	1	3,33	-	-	12	8,00
Disagree	11	36,66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	7,34
Amount	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	30	100	150	100

Source: processed data, 2019

Tugu Khatulistiwa respondents showed that respondents felt difficulties, distance and the condition of the facilities that are not well maintained. RTH Waterfront shows respondents assume that the existing facilities are not yet fully used or are still in the stage of repair / development. The RTH Korem and Untan Garden produced positive respondents' opinions, they argued that the design of the RTH about the location of existing facilities was well organized, so that the visitors had no difficulty in finding and leaving all the existing facilities. RTH Akcaya Garden shows that respondents consider the lack of facilities to accommodate RTH visitors.

V. Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion that has been presented previously, it was concluded that the perception of the majority of respondents on the management of Green Open Space in general is already good, but it is undeniable that there are still a small number of respondents arguing that they do not agree with the management of Green Open Space that has been able to meet the RTH standards as needs Public.

VI. Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the researchers recommend:

- 1) The good response of visitors to Green Open Space reflects the community's need for Green Open Space in Pontianak City is very important, thus the local government can increase the quantity of Green Open Space according to the minimum standard of 30% according to the Spatial Planning Law, as well as having icons to be characteristic typical.

- 2) Every Green Open Space can provide facilities and infrastructure (cleanliness, security, playground, sports, seating, etc.) according to the standard of spatial planning that can be used properly, and can be reached by various groups (including people with disabilities).
- 3) The existence of supervision in the management of maintaining Green Open Space, local governments can involve the community / local communities / various stakeholders in maintaining facilities and infrastructure facilities in order to realize the quality of the Green Open Space.
- 4) In the construction of a new Green Open Space that can consider the location to be built, the strategic location will be able to increase the quantity of visitors, easy access and crowded centers is one of the factors that can be considered in determining strategic locations.

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